

STUDIES ON SULPHONAMIDES AND ANALOGOUS COMPOUNDS.
PART V. N⁴-SUBSTITUTION

BY U. P. BASU, SUDHAMOY MUKHERJEE AND A. N. BOSE

Characteristic differences in sulphacetamide and sulphanyilbenzamide after substitution of the *p*-amido hydrogen by phthaly radical have been studied and discussed.

As the basic amino group in sulfa drugs plays a vital part in producing bacteriostasis, attempts are often being made to produce their N⁴-substituted derivatives in order to lower their toxicity and/or to widen their activity. The drug action is believed to be due to the formation of a drug-enzyme complex with the enzyme of the pathogenic organisms, and any difference in the activity between the two drugs is ascribed to be due to the relative dissociation constants of sulphonamide-enzyme complexes formed at the body *p_a* (cf. Klötz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 459; Woods, *Brit. J. Exp. Path.*, 1940, 21, 74; Sevag, *Adv. Enzymol.*, 1946, 6, 33). But as no definite idea is yet known about the various complex enzyme systems, numerous derivatives of sulfa compounds are being prepared in the expectation of isolating a compound which may reach the site of infection in adequate concentration (cf. Poth and Ross, *J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1944, 29, 785; Bonchart, *J. Dig. Med.*, 1946, 18, 629; Basu, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 130).

In the course of our investigations phthalylsulphacetamide and phthalylsulphanilylbenzamide (Sikdar and Basu, this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 345) were prepared and their solubility in water and that again in presence of a phosphate buffer, their dissociation exponent and bacteriostatic activity were studied and the results recorded in this paper. The former compound has been recently noted to be clinically effective in typhoid fever (cf. Wright, *Canad. Med. Assoc. J.*, 1949, 61, 63).

EXPERIMENTAL

N⁴-Phthalylsulphacetamide.—A mixture of sulphacetamide (10.7 g.) and freshly sublimed phthalic anhydride (7.4 g.) was dissolved in acetone (40 c.c.) with shaking. The solution was filtered and the filtrate was left aside at the room temperature (25-26°); crystals began to separate out and were collected after a few hours. They were recrystallised from alcohol in fine prismatic needles, m.p. 202°. (Found: N, 7.6. C₁₆H₁₄O₆N₂S requires N, 7.74 per cent). The substance is insoluble in ether, and sparingly soluble in boiling water. It, however, dissolves readily in sodium bicarbonate solution and may be precipitated out on acidification with dilute acid. The compound is very susceptible to hydrolysis and is readily hydrolysable in presence of dilute alkali to *p*-aminobenzene sulphonacetamide.

N⁴-Phthalylsulphanilylbenzamide.—The compound used in the course of this investigation was prepared by the method previously described (Sikdar and Basu, *loc. cit.*) and was found to melt at 224-25°.

Physical Characteristics.—A study has been made of some physical and chemical properties of phthalylsulphacetamide and phthalylsulphabenzamide. Solubilities were determined in water and in 0.2 M phosphate buffer solutions. The aqueous solutions were also titrated potentiometrically with caustic soda solution. The data are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Particulars.	Phthalylsulphacetamide.	Phthalylsulphabenzamide.
Solubility in water (at 30°).	110 mg./100 c.c. $p_H=2.8$	mg./100 c.c. $p_H=4.38$
Solubility in phosphate buffers	436 mg./100 c.c. $p_H=4.19$ 910 mg./100 c.c. $p_H=5.53$	154 mg./100 c.c. $p_H=5.57$ 705 mg./100 c.c. $p_H=5.88$
Dissociation exponent calculated from p_H at half neutralisation	$pK_{a1}=3.86$ (pK_{a1} for phthalic acid = 2.9)	(pK_{a1} for sulphabenzamide = 4.57)
Dissociation exponent for the second stage of neutralisation from half neutralisation	$pK_{a2}=5.3$ (pK_{a2} for sulphacetamide = 5.38)	$pK_{a2}=8.52$
Dissociation exponent for the 3rd stage	$pK_{a3}=6.6$ (pK_{a3} for phthalic acid = 5.51)	$pK_{a3}=9.93$
Appearance of aqueous solution	Clear	Opalescent

The potentiometric titration curve (curve I in Figure 1) for sulphacetamide has two breaks, the first inflexion occurring on the addition of exactly one-third of the amount of alkali required at the final inflexion. The compound thus appears to behave as a tribasic acid in which the second and third stages of neutralisation overlap each other so that the second break in the curve is not perceptible. The first stage of neutralisation

FIG. 1

Curves I and II refer respectively to phthalyl-sulphacetamide and a sulph-benzamide.

corresponds to a p_{ka} value 3.32 calculated from the p_n at half neutralisation using the equation,

$$p_k = p_n + \log \frac{C - [B] - [H^+] + \frac{k_w}{[H^+]}}{[B] + [H^+] - \frac{k_w}{[H^+]}}$$

This value is somewhat higher than the dissociation exponent of phthalic acid for which p_{ka} is 2.9. For the second stage, the value of p_{ka} calculated in the same way, is 5.31, which agrees closely with that for sulphacetamide, namely, 5.38. The value of p_{ka} for the third stage comes to 6.6.

It may be supposed that the first stage represents the neutralisation of the free carboxyl group of phthalic acid, this bearing the strongest acid group. The second stage appears to correspond to a neutralisation of the replaceable hydrogen atom in the sulphamido group of sulphacetamide in view of the close agreement between the dissociation constants. During the third stage of neutralisation, the gradual hydrolytic breakdown of the phthalimido group and the simultaneous neutralisation of the second carboxyl group of phthalic acid with alkali may be envisaged. The apparent dissociation exponent under these conditions would be higher than the true value for the free acidic group, as is actually found to be the case (*i.e.*, 6.6 in place of 5.51).

The hydrolytic breakdown, supposed to occur at the third stage, would be accompanied with the regeneration of the free amino group and the formation of alkali phthalate. Diazo reaction using sodium nitrite and β -naphthol actually confirmed the presence of the free amino group. The unneutralised solution of the phthalyl compound did not respond to this test.

From the merging of the second and the third stages of neutralisation it may be inferred that the hydrolytic breakdown sets in even during the second stage. This was also confirmed by the diazo test when the solution at p_n 6.0 gave a somewhat feeble coloration. This p_n corresponds to the completion of the second stage of neutralisation in the titration curve.

The titration curve for phthalylsulphabenzamide (curve II) shows essentially similar features, the first inflexion point corresponding to one third of the amount of alkali added at the second and final inflexion. Here also the second and third stages of neutralisation overlap. The p_k values corresponding to the three stages are 5.13, 8.53 and 9.93. If the three stages represent, as postulated in the other case, respectively the neutralisation of the free carboxyl of the phthalic acid, that of the dissociable hydrogen atom, and the hydrolysis of the phthalyl group, it follows that the ionisations of the acidic groups have been depressed much more here than in the case of phthalylsulphacetamide.

Bacteriostatic Activity.—The bacteriostatic activity of the compounds was studied against the organisms as recorded in Table II. Each of the drugs was incorporated in 1% peptone water (p_n 7.5) in requisite concentration.

TABLE II

Culture: 18 hours in 1% peptone water. Inoculum=500 cells in each case. Incubation temp. =37.0°. Period of observation =72 hrs.

Figures indicate minimum bacteriostatic concentration in mg. per 100 c.c. of the medium.

Compounds.	Organisms				
	<i>E. Typhosa.</i>	<i>Para Typhi B.</i>	<i>Sonnel.</i>	<i>P. exner</i> Y.	<i>B. Pyocyane.</i>
Sulphacetamide	<50 >25	50	12.5	25	25
Sulphanilylbenzamide	..	50	<6.25	<6.25	100
Phthalylsulphacetamide	..	50	6.25	6.25	12.5
Phthalylsulphanilylbenzamide	..	50	<6.25	6.25	25

From Table II it would be noticed that all the compounds are equally effective against *E. typhosa* and *S. paratyphi B.* They are more bacteriostatic against dysentery organism. The enhanced activity of phthalylsulphacetamide against *B. Pyocyane* may also be noticed.

The ready susceptibility of the phthalylsulphacetamide to hydrolysis in alkaline condition may set up a condition in the system that will be responsible for its reported activity in typhoid infections. The compound is being clinically evaluated.